

CUPRIC HYDROXIDE SOL.

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Cupric hydroxide sol has been prepared and its various properties with coagulation, abnormal dilution effect, ionic antagonism etc. have been investigated.

Very little work has been done on the preparation of cupric hydroxide sol in the absence of protective agents like cane sugar (Sen and Dhar, *Kolloid Z.*, 1923, **33**, 193), grape sugar, casein, sodium salts of protalbinic and lysalbinic acids etc. which have been found to stabilise cupric hydroxide sols. Kohlshutter (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1919 **25**, 309) reported the formation of a sol when a current of high density was passed between copper electrodes in dilute copper sulphate solution. Burton (*Phil. Mag.*, 1906, **11**, 436) prepared a positively charged unstable cupric hydroxide sol by passing a spark between copper electrodes under water. Hooker (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, **15**, 1177) obtained a blue sol by washing the gelatinous precipitate of cupric hydroxide formed by adding alkali to copper sulphate solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In an attempt to prepare a pure sol of cupric hydroxide, it was found that copper sulphate is not a satisfactory starting material because of the coagulating effect of the sulphate ions on the sol formed. Cupric chloride was, however, found to be a suitable starting material for this sol. A dilute solution of ammonium hydroxide was added very gradually to a solution of cupric chloride when the amount was just sufficient to throw down a gelatinous precipitate of cupric hydroxide. The precipitate was allowed to settle, the supernatant liquid decanted off and finally the compact precipitate was peptised with minimum quantity of water, when a dirty blue sol resulted. The undialysed sol was taken for investigation. It was further purified by cold dialysis to different extents for further studies. The following are the results obtained.

TABLE I.

Concentration and purity.

	Sol I. (Undialysed)	Sol II. (Dialysed for 48 hrs.)	Sol III. (Dialysed for 96 hrs.)
CuO (g./litre)	3.26	2.54	1.98
Chloride „	3.41	1.93	1.59
Purity	0.448	0.62	0.60

TABLE II.

Coagulation.

The sols were maintained at the same concentration *i.e.*, 1.63 g. of CuO per litre. Sol taken each time = 5 c.c. Total volume = 10 c.c. Time for complete coagulation = 1 hour.

Sol conc.	Sol I.			Ratio KCl K ₂ SO ₄
	Precipitating concentration KCl.	NH ₄ Cl.	K ₂ SO ₄ .	
Sol I	0.165M	0.190M	0.000425M	388
Sol I/2	0.180	0.220	0.000275	655
Sol I/4	0.195	0.250	0.000175	1114
Sol II.				
Sol II	0.225	...	0.00035	620
Sol II/2	0.235	...	0.00022	1068
Sol II/4	0.245	...	0.00017	1441
Sol III.				
Sol III	0.220	...	0.00022	1000
Sol III/2	0.227	...	0.00016	1419
Sol III/4	0.235	...	0.00012	1958

TABLE III.

Coagulation with mixture of KCl and K₂SO₄.

N/200-K₂SO₄ for complete coagulation.

Sol I.						
N/2-KCl (c.c.)	...	0	3.3	1.0	2.0	3.0
Obs.	...	1.7	0	1.8	1.5	0.7
Calc.	1.19	0.67	0.15
Diff.	0.61	0.83	0.55

TABLE III (*contd.*).

Sol II.						
$N/2$ -KCl (c.c.)	..	0	4.5	1.0	2.0	3.0
Obs.	...	1.4	0	1.5	1.3	0.9
Calc.	1.09	0.77	0.47
Diff.	0.41	0.53	0.43
Sol III.						
$N/2$ -KCl (c.c.)	...	0	4.4	1.0	2.0	3.0
Obs.	...	0.9	0	1.0	0.9	0.6
Calc.	0.7	0.5	0.29
Diff.	0.3	0.4	0.31

TABLE IV.

Viscosity of the sol at 35°.

	Viscosity.	Density.
Sol I	1.06	1.021
Sol II	1.04	1.015
Sol III	1.03	1.009
Water	1.00	...

A fresh sample of the sol was prepared and subjected to hot dialysis to different extents. The following were the results obtained.

TABLE V.

Concentration and purity.

	Sol A. (Dialysed hot for 50 hours).	Sol B. (Dialysed hot for 90 hours.)
CuO (g./litre)	7.34	6.99
Chloride (,,)	2.59	1.98
Purity	1.33	1.66

TABLE VI.

Coagulation.

The sols were maintained at the same concentration of 1.63 g of CuO per litre. Sol taken each time = 5 c.c. Total volume = 10 c.c. Time for complete coagulation = 1 hour.

Sol conc.		Precipitating concentrations.			
		KCl.	KBrO ₃ .	KIO ₃ .	K ₂ SO ₄ .
Sol A.					
Sol A	...	0.11M	0.023M	0.0028M	0.00032M
A/2	...	0.12	0.023	0.0028	0.00019
A/4	...	0.13	0.025	0.0028	...
Sol. B.					
Sol B	...	0.02M	0.019M	0.0024M	0.00029M
B/2	..	0.021	0.020	0.0024	...
B/4	...	0.023	0.022	0.0024	...
Ratios of ppt. conc.					
		KCl.	KBrO ₃ .	KIO ₃ .	K ₂ SO ₄ .
Sol A	...	344	72	9	1
Sol B	...	67	65	8	1

TABLE VII.

*Coagulation with mixture of KCl and K₂SO₄.**N/400-K₂SO₄ for complete coagulation.*

	Sol A.				Sol B.				
	0	2.2	1.0	1.5	0	4.0	2.0	3.0	
N/2-KCl (c.c.)...	0	2.2	1.0	1.5	0	4.0	2.0	3.0	
Obs.	...	2.6	0	1.3	0.7	2.3	0	1.22	0.55
Calc.	1.4	0.8	1.15	0.58
Diff.	0.1	0.1	0.07	0.03

TABLE VIII.

Viscosity of the sols at 35°.

Sol.			Viscosity.	Density.
Sol A	1.06	1.04
Sol B	1.05	1.03
Water	1.00	—

DISCUSSION.

From the foregoing results it may be seen that cupric hydroxide sol could not be obtained in so highly concentrated condition as the sols previously studied (Mittra and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 315). To whatever lengths of time the sols were dialysed for purification, they could not be freed completely from their respective stabilising ions. This high adsorbability of the stabilising ions did not allow the development of lyophilic character of the sols, for the viscosities of the sols were not different from the typically lyophobic ones. It must be emphasised here that in sols behaving in a lyophilic manner like those of ferric hydroxide, aluminium hydroxide, etc., the higher the hydration, the less is the charge on the colloid particles and conversely higher charge on the colloid particles is responsible for low viscosity of the sol. It has been shown (Dhar and Mittra, *Kolloid Z.*, 1935, 71, 172) that by adding thorium nitrate to a purified sol of thorium hydroxide of a high viscosity, it became less viscous. From the precipitating concentrations of the electrolytes and their ratios for different valencies it may also be seen that the sols were very impure, and the purity data supported that.

It may be observed here that the amounts of a monovalent ion, such as chloride, required to coagulate the sols of cupric hydroxide increased with the progressive dialysis of the sols and finally decreased. Similarly the ratios of the precipitating concentrations, mono: bi: tri: quadri-valent ions had tendency to decrease (Table VI). It is a general experience that the sols, prepared by the interaction of two or more substances in solutions, producing electrolytes as resultants, should immediately be dialysed as soon as they are prepared, for the electrolytes present in the sols have a coagulating influence, though it is a very slow process. It is necessary at this stage to mention the results of Desai and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 463) on the stability of gold and ferric hydroxide sols on dialysis. These authors report that in general, the electric charge on colloid particles increases, passes through a maximum and then quickly falls with the progressive dialysis.

The experimental results on the coagulation of cupric hydroxide sols of different concentrations and degrees of purity, prepared by hot and cold dialysis, indicate that greater quantities of potassium chloride or ammonium chloride are necessary to coagulate a dilute sol than a concentrated one, and this abnormal behaviour of dilution towards potassium chloride is more prominent with impure sols than with purer ones. The sol prepared by hot dialysis also develops this phenomenon though less prominently. It has been reported (Ghosh and Mittra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 10, 471) that

change of stability of sols of various concentrations is ultimately related with their purity, besides the effect of the similarly charged ions as has been emphasised by Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 647). It has been shown by the author that sols of ferric, aluminium, chromium (*cf.* Mittra and Dhar, *loc. cit.*) and thorium hydroxides (*cf.* Dhar and Mittra, *loc. cit.*) are stable towards electrolytes like potassium chloride on dilution, when large quantities of stabilising electrolytes are present.

It has already been pointed out that in the cases of impure sols, the abnormal behaviour on dilution towards its coagulation by monovalent electrolytes develops in the presence of large amounts of stabilising electrolytes but the additive relationship for the electrolytes of different valencies is maintained, provided the sol is incapable of adsorbing the similarly charged ions of the added electrolytes. The results in Table III show that amounts of potassium sulphate greater than the calculated amounts are necessary to coagulate a cupric hydroxide sol, purified by cold dialysis in the presence of potassium chloride; in other words, ionic antagonism is observed in coagulating this sol by a mixture of potassium chloride and potassium sulphate. In order to see how far the adsorption of similarly charged ions is responsible for such behaviour of cupric hydroxide sol, the following experiments were performed on the adsorption of ammonium and chloride ions from ammonium chloride by different amounts of copper hydroxide.

A definite volume (50 c. c.) of the sol was taken in separate graduated 100 c. c. flasks. The sols were coagulated by definite amounts of potassium sulphate. To one of the flasks 10 c. c. of the standardised ammonium chloride solution (5 c. c. of which contained 0.145 g. of ammonium chloride) and to the other 20 c. c. of it were added, while the third one was kept without it. All the three were made upto 100 c. c. by water and kept overnight. The supernatant clear liquid (5 c. c.) was carefully pipetted out from each of the three flasks and heated on water-baths with excess of standard potassium hydroxide solution. The unacted potassium hydroxide was titrated back with standard hydrochloric acid in each case, from which the ammonium equivalents were determined. The amounts of ammonium ions, already present while preparing the sol, was determined from the third flask with no extra ammonium chloride and subtracted from the total amount of ammonium ions from each of the other two flasks. Similarly the amounts of the chloride ions unadsorbed from the added ammonium chloride were estimated from the first two flasks.

Similar experiments were repeated by taking 25 c. c. of the sol, keeping the other conditions the same.

TABLE IX.

	% Adsorption with 10 c.c. of NH_4Cl .		% Adsorption with 20 c.c. NH_4Cl .	
	NH_4	Cl.	NH_4 .	Cl.
Sol (50 c.c.)	17'2	13'4	35'0	11'54
Sol (25 c.c.)	8'0	4'6	11'4	1'80

The above experiment clearly proves that cupric hydroxide can adsorb appreciable amounts of cations like NH_4 from NH_4Cl solution. It will be also noted here that the adsorption of Cl ions is small in comparison to NH_4 ions and further the ratio of the percentage of adsorption of NH_4 ions to that of Cl ions increases with the decreasing amount of the adsorbent. These results confirm the views of Ghosh and Dhar (*loc cit.*) on the abnormal behaviour of sols on dilution in the cases where the ions, carrying the same charge as the colloid particles, from a coagulating electrolyte, play an important part. The above experimental results, therefore, prove that the stability of cupric hydroxide sol on dilution towards its coagulation by ammonium chloride is partly due to the adsorption of the similarly charged cation from ammonium chloride and partly due to the large amount of the stabilising electrolyte present in the sol.

Ghosh and Dhar have concluded that for the sols which are capable of adsorbing the ions carrying the same charge as the colloid particles from a coagulating electrolyte, abnormal dilution effect, ionic antagonism and the phenomenon of acclimatisation are developed. The following results were obtained by the present author on the phenomenon of acclimatisation of cupric hydroxide sols dialysed in the cold when coagulated by NH_4Cl .

TABLE X.

Time allowed for the coagulation to proceed = 24 hours.

	A m o u n t of $\text{N}/2\text{-KCl}$ a d d e d all at once.	by parts.
Sol I	2'25 c.c.	5'0 c.c.
Sol II	3'1	4'5
Sol III	3'0	4'2

The results presented in Tables II and III show that the abnormal dilution effect for the coagulation of cupric hydroxide sol by KCl and the ionic antagonism for a mixture of KCl and K_2SO_4 for this sol become less

prominent when the sol is dialysed to greater extents. Similarly the results in Tables VI and VII show that both the abnormal dilution effect and ionic antagonism are not so prominent in the sol prepared by hot dialysis as observed with the impure sample of cupric hydroxide sol obtained by cold dialysis. Also the capability for adsorption of cations like K or NH_4 by cupric hydroxide greatly diminishes with ageing, which is considerably hastened by the process of heating.

It may be of interest to discuss here some of the results of Sorum and Judd (*J. Amer Chem Soc.* 1930, **52**, 2591) on the stability of ferric hydroxide sol. These authors report that the Burton-Bishop rule or so-called abnormal dilution effect of Ghosh and Dhar is observable with this sol when it is purified to its extreme extent. My results on the coagulation of ferric hydroxide sol prepared by acetate method lead to conclusions opposed to those of Sorum and Judd. It has been found that ferric hydroxide sol of purity 63.28 showed abnormal dilution effect towards its coagulation with electrolytes, while the sol which was highly pure and whose purity could not be determined showed normal effect.

In the opinion of the present author if a sol is not sufficiently pure and contains large amounts of the stabilising electrolytes, the sol may behave abnormally towards the coagulation by univalent electrolytes on dilution, inspite of the fact that the sol is incapable of adsorbing similarly charged ions from the coagulating electrolytes leading to the additive relationship when the sol is coagulated by a mixture of electrolytes.

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PLATE I.

PLATE II.

